

**93rd Annual Meeting of the German
Society of Glass Technology (DGG) in
conjunction with the
French Union for Science and Glass
Technology (USTV) Annual Meeting
Nürnberg, Germany**

13. - 15. May 2019

Abstracts

Deutsche
Glastechnische Gesellschaft e. V.

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FunGlass

Design of sol-gel media and inkjet printing of mullite

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Abstract

This work focuses on direct inkjet printing of sol-gel-based precursors using commercially available and low-cost printer to fabricate complex ceramic features with high spatial resolution. We re-engineered the printer by modifying the hardware, while preserving the printer's ability to be controlled by conventional software. The hardware upgrade enables fluid deposition on solid substrates with the print accuracy and precision close to unmodified printer using thermal ink cartridges. Although this method of printing promises high processing speeds, there remain significant issues of premature clogging of inkjet printheads when printing aqueous sols. To avoid clogging on internal surfaces of the printhead a systematic design of inkjet inks is needed. The design must address ink rheology, colloidal stability and suppress cracks formation during firing. Water based inks with low viscosity and moderate surface tension were designed. The rheological properties of the ink have been determined by viscosity, surface tension and contact angle measurements. Drying of the precursor yields composite powders forming mullite structure after firing at 1300°C, as confirmed by X-ray powder diffraction before realizing the inkjet printing. The quality of printed patterns like line stability, edge acuity and cross-section of the lines was characterized using confocal optical microscopy. Proper adjustment of quantities of each component and processing conditions resulted in preparation of stoichiometric $3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$ mullite layer in one step process.